

MODERN TECHNOLOGIES AND WEBSITES FOR TEACHING THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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ANNOTATION

This article discusses effective methods for teaching other languages as well as the use of internet and contemporary technologies in English language instruction.

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INTRODUCTION

Today, our nation, like many other advanced nations, elevates the teaching of several foreign languages in addition to the state language to the level of state policy. A number of draught laws are being developed to ensure that the broad spectrum of foreign language learning and teaching is actively involved in major reforms. The Presidential Decree "On measures to further improve the system of teaching foreign languages" enacted on December 10, 2012 thereby increased the options for studying foreign languages as a natural extension of these concepts [1]. Nowadays, the majority of public and private firms look for people with strong English skills and the necessary credentials. The government is giving the teaching of the English language in Uzbekistan's schools and universities a lot of attention because of the importance of the English language in educational curriculum. In Uzbekistan's universities and schools, English is taught as a required subject, and the government is working hard to support effective English teaching and learning [2].

Young pupils will learn English more quickly if their interest in the subject is increased, their possibilities are expanded, and they are given support. It is essential to expand the following: the availability of diverse electronic resources; the development of methodological support for language learning in educational institutions; the effectiveness of employing current textbooks; and the recruitment of capable and capable professionals to the teaching process.

Focus on student motivation in teaching and control the quality of the assessment system. Adequate inclusion of new educational technology into the educational process. Focus on student motivation in teaching and regulate the quality of the evaluation system.

Increased speech expressions where the majority of the material is obtained from everyday life are a sign that English language instruction is being controlled for quality and effectiveness. Evaluation of the lesson's creative technology utilisation as a tool for language teaching and learning yields a variety of advantageous outcomes.

Innovation. Innovation (also known as "innovasion" in English) is innovation. Innovative technologies have a significant role in the execution of the instructional process and the activities of instructors and students. The work done to improve students' thinking, imagination, worldview, and interests reflects the use of cutting-edge technologies. McCarthy claims that "over the past 50 years, the methodology of teaching foreign languages has undergone significant development. It has been conducted at various times in grammatical translation, audio-linguistic structure, global audiovisual, inductive/deductive, functional, ideational, situational, communicative, immersion, learning/receiving, recommendation, etc. Consequently, as a result of the use of audiovisual tools during the lesson, the ability to remember the semantic meaning of words and use lexical units improves. [3]

Information communication technologies. The role of modern pedagogical technologies and information and communication tools in improving the quality and efficiency of education, in the purposeful organization of game-based lessons that interest students is very large. is becoming an integral part of the process. In order to teach English to young people through a computer, first of all, the teacher himself must be able to use computer technologies at a professional level. including the ability to organize new training programs. In order to become a pedagogue of this level, every foreign language teacher needs to work more on himself in the field of modern technologies. Computer-based English language teaching has several advantages compared to traditional teaching methods. First of all, a computer-based English language learner has four areas of language skills (speaking, listening, writing, and reading). will have the opportunity to test their skills. Currently, this is possible with the help of advanced programs. It is only necessary to be able to properly direct the student to this method of education.

In addition, it has been proven that every rule, every word, every concept unit taught in the teaching of foreign languages with the help of a computer is better stored in the student's memory. the ability to deliver in the form of video makes teaching foreign languages through the computer one of the most effective methods. Therefore, every teacher needs to use the rich possibilities of the computer in teaching English to his students through the computer. Basically, it is appropriate to use Word and Power Point programs to explain current topics. Because I think that students will understand

much easier if the topic is explained using table views through the Word program. In Power Point, students can be more attracted to the topic by showing these topics in audio, picture and video formats.

Educational technologies. The most crucial task of the educational process is the student's personal interest, and one of the main tasks is to improve the teacher's pedagogical skills by mastering modern teaching and learning technologies. With the use of any new technologies, the teacher's pedagogical ideas begin to change: the teacher's systematic, methodological language becomes clearer, and clear tactics in the teaching methodology emerge. Pedagogical (educational) technology is a well-thought-out model of educational and pedagogical activity combined with a comfortable environment for students and teachers to design, organize and conduct the educational process. Pedagogical technology includes the implementation of the idea of full control of the educational process [4]. Modern educational technologies include:

- development;
- studying problems;
- multi-level education;
- collective education system;
- technological study of inventive problems;
- research methods in teaching;
- project teaching methods;

Technology used in teaching game styles:

- role-playing, business and other types of educational games;
- cooperative education (community, group work);
- information and communication technologies;

When it comes to design and interactive teaching methods, their combination and integration is considered one of the most effective and efficient tools in the process of teaching English. One of them is the project method. The project method is designed to develop a child's active independent thinking and teach him not only to memorize and reproduce knowledge, but also to apply it in practice. It is important that children learn to cooperate when working on a project, and cooperative education helps to strengthen mutual support, desire and ability, and students' creative abilities and activities are formed. The project method is a set of educational and knowledge techniques that allow solving certain problems as a result of the mandatory presentation of these results as a result of independent actions of students. The project method is an activity that allows students to express themselves independently, individually or in a group, to test their abilities, the teacher to apply his knowledge in practice, to show the results achieved

by the public. This method involves solving interesting problems created by students themselves. For example, "Why am I late for class today?" i.e. "Why am I late for class today?" the question is asked. In this way, students try to express their knowledge through a foreign language, and they do not repeat this situation by showing their trivial reasons to other students [5].

The design method as a pedagogical technology is a technology that includes a combination of research, research, and problem-solving methods. For students, the project is an opportunity to increase their creative potential to the maximum level, and in principle, in order to solve the problem, students should have clear creative, intellectual and communicative skills. Therefore, for the correct use of the project method, extensive training is required, which is carried out in an integrated educational system.

Interactive methods. Active or interactive methods involve the stimulation of cognitive activity and learner autonomy. Interactive methods are aimed at creating a comfortable learning environment where all students actively communicate with each other. The organization of interactive education includes the modeling of life conditions, the use of role-playing games, the general solution of information based on the analysis of tasks and situations, the introduction of information flows into the mind, which causes its active activity. An integral part of interactive approaches are interactive exercises and tasks performed by students. The main difference between interactive exercises and regular work is that they are aimed not only at consolidating the learned material, but also at learning new things [6].

Modern pedagogy is rich in many interactive approaches, including:

- creative tasks - work in small groups - educational games (role playing, imitation, business games and educational games)
- use of public resources (inviting specialists, excursions) — social projects (social projects, contests, radio and newspapers, films, demonstrations, exhibitions, performances, songs and tales)
- learning and strengthening of new materials (interactive working with lecture, demonstration manuals, video and audio materials, "student as teacher", "everyone teaches everyone")
- discussion of complex and controversial questions and problems. [7]

With the interactive education method, students communicate directly in the learning environment, which in turn serves as a source of experience. In the understanding of pedagogical methods, it implies the preparation of students and teachers when mutual relations are formed. He does not work as a student-listener or

observer, but actively participates in the lesson. With this form of organization of the educational process, not only school, high school, college, and even higher education students become full participants. The task of the teacher is mainly to encourage independent activity, to find ways to achieve their goals [2]. Thus, by using various pedagogical technologies in the lesson, the process of teaching English can be viewed from a completely new perspective, new mechanisms of personality formation can be mastered, and quality results can be achieved under favorable conditions.

CONCLUSION

The conclusion is that today's era of globalization requires humanity to keep up with the times. Therefore, it is desirable for specialists of various fields to be able to communicate in several foreign languages in addition to having a perfect knowledge of their native language. It is no secret that on May 6, 2021, a meeting of video selectors was held under the chairmanship of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev regarding measures to improve the system of teaching foreign languages. In it, the head of our state said, "It's time to establish a new system for teaching foreign languages in our country, which will be a solid foundation for the future. Since we have set ourselves the goal of building a competitive country, from now on, graduates of schools, lyceums, colleges and universities must have a perfect knowledge of at least 2 foreign languages. This strict requirement should become the main criterion for the activity of the head of every educational institution", he said, bringing reforms in the field to a new level.

This strict requirement should become the main criterion for the activity of the head of every educational institution since we have set ourselves the goal of building a competitive country, he said, bringing reforms in the field to a new level. "Graduates of schools, lyceums, colleges and universities must now have a perfect knowledge of at least two foreign languages," he said.

Considering the widespread use of technology and various websites in the study of various modern sciences, [8]the use of the above in the process of teaching and learning English is the most effective method. The use of such tools among language teachers, firstly, considers the theoretical, methodological and practical issues of foreign language teaching in modern education.

REFERENCES :

1. Axmedova S. R. и др. Masofaviy ta'lim va uning horijiy tillarni o'qitishdagi o'rni //Science and Education. – 2021. – T. 2. – №. 10. – C. 608-612.
2. Axmedova, S. R. (2021). Chet tillarni o'rganish va undagi metodlarning ahamiyati. Science and Education, 2(11), 1076-1080.

3. Boswood, T. (1997). *New Ways of Using Computers in Language Teaching* (New Ways in Tesol Series II), California: Teachers of English to Speakers of Other Languages.

4. Harmer, J. (2007). *How to teach English*, Harlow, Essex: Pearson-Longman

5. Johnson, D., & Eisenberg, M. (2006). *Learning and Teaching Information Technology-- Computer Skills in Context*, East Lansing, Mi, Eric document ED465377, Retrieved June 7, 2007, from <http://www.ericdigests.org/2003-1/skills.htm>.

6. Warschauer, M., & Kern, K. (2000). *Network-based Language Teaching: Concepts and Practice*, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.

7. Xorijiy tillarni o'rgatishda rol o'ynash o'yinlari // INR №4, 1989

8. Ingliz tilini o'qitish bo'yicha loyiha ustida ishlash // INR Xorijiy tillarni o'qitish metodikasi usuli // INR №2, 3, 2000 Ingliz va o'zbek tillarining funktsional uslub

WEBSITES:

1. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/o-quvchilarga-ingliz-tilini-o-qitishda-innovatsion-texnologiyalar-va-interaktiv-metodlarning-ahamiyati/viewer>

2. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/ingliz-tilini-o-qitish-va-o-rganishda-zamonaviy-texnologiyalardan-foydalanish>

3. <https://moluch.ru/archive/309/69718/>

